

The Impact of Social Stratification to the Phenomenon of "Terrorism"

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Abstract—In this work social stratification is considered as one of significant factor which generate the phenomena “terrorism” and it puts the accent on correlation connection between them, with the object of creation info-logical model generation of phenomena of “terrorism” based on stratification process.

Keywords—Social stratification, stratification process, generation of phenomena “terrorism”, conceptions – “terror”, “terrorize” and “terrorism”, info-logical model of phenomena of “terrorism”.

I. INTRODUCTION

TERRORISM is known to mankind since ancient times, from the time when the power over other people began to bring people certain material benefits. And the power turned into the object of desire of individuals who wanted achieve their goals by any means, including violence, that is, the history of terror began with the history of the struggle for power in the tribe, the clan, in the state, and in the empire. The end justifies the means, and the power-hungry person, did not hesitate to use the most brutal and extreme measures [1]. This shows that the initial cause of the violence and terror was exactly the stratification of society, i.e. exfoliation of society.

However, in the XXI century, terrorism has moved into first place in the number of not only national, domestic threats, but also international security. Terrorism is being illegal for centuries, but quite an effective weapon in the political struggle, has become one of the most important factors of social destabilization in the world. Today, from outbreaks of terrorism are not insured highly, no lag in economic and social development of the country with the different political regimes and political notions [2]. Since for all of humanity, the XX century was a period of transition from the industrial age to the information. In this context, social stratification has played a key role in both the development and safety of various societies.

Since the late 60s, it (terrorism) became truly alarming issue: in the period from 1970 to 1985 acts of terrorism has committed: in Europe about 3000, and in Latin America – 1573, in the Middle East - 1330, and in North America – 448. Since 1986, the number of increase in terrorist acts in different parts of the world made up to 50 to 60 percent. Along with the fact that the number of attacks is increasing, they are becoming more violent and mostly people are becoming their

object. Thus, in 1970s 80% of the attacks were directed against property and only 20% - against people, in 1980s, it was directed to respectively, 50% and 50%, in 1990s 30% and 70%. Acts of terrorism are carefully prepared with the result that 90% of terrorist attacks, in some way, achieve their goals. Increased dramatically within the discipline of terrorist organizations started to strengthen the discipline within them, terrorist groups from different countries started cooperating with each other to coordinate and globalize their actions. There is a constant development of forms and methods of carrying out terrorist activities, networking and exchange of experience between terrorist groups, including those with a global communications on the Internet [3]. In this context, the phenomenon of “terrorism” became a dynamic system is an inseparable part of the society accelerating the stratification process.

Modern terrorism - is a complex, and a lot of very negative aspect of social and political phenomenon that went beyond the national borders of individual states and turned into a large-scale threat to the security of the entire world community. [4].

In these circumstances, the problem of effective counter-terrorism have become the subject of careful and committed study by political scientists, lawyers, sociologists, legislators, law enforcement and intelligence services [5]. Recently, there appeared a lot of work in the literature associated with the modeling of the phenomenon of "terrorism" [6], which attempts to create a unified model of this phenomenon to study the dialectical basis of its generation. The analysis of these works shows that a single model of the phenomenon of "terrorism" does not currently exist, because by its nature the phenomenon of "terrorism" is a multidimensional framework that includes, for example, criminal, religious, political and other aspects. So when it comes to models of the phenomenon of "terrorism" [7], we should also consider distinguishing between concepts such as "terror", "terrorism" and "terrorize" [8]. These concepts allow tracing the correlation between the process of stratification in society and a product of the phenomenon of "terrorism", to reveal their mutual influence and create a logical model of information-generating.

Terror is a system of political, social, economic, criminal, and religious measures used by the state or other organizations on the massive violence and the maintenance of fear among the population for unquestioning obedience to the political regime [9]. This is the beginning of the implementation of social stratification.

The above assumes that the aggravation of the social stratification, as a result of terror, also proportionally increases

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probability that the phenomenon of terrorism in society, because the social stratification maybe one of the possible causes of all the economic, political, criminal, religious and social background of the phenomenon "terrorism", which is based on "violence", "terrorization".

Terrorization – is a signs of a criminal act of terrorism was committed for the sake of creating an environment of fear by which affects third parties to achieve the ultimate goal [10].

Terrorism – is a violation, use of force, and other acts that endanger persons or property, or the threat of them to compel public authorities, international organizations and their officials, or the person or entity to do or abstain from doing any activity to complicate international relations, violation of the sovereignty and territorial integrity, undermining state security, provoking war, armed conflict and the destabilization of the political situation, terrorizing the population, as well as activities aimed at ensuring the existence, functioning and financing of the terrorist organization, preparation and commission of terrorist acts, directly or indirectly, provision or collection of any funds, resources, and other services to terrorist organizations or persons assisting or participating in terrorist activities [11].

Such a distinction of the concepts of "terror", "terrorism" and "terrorizing" explains the process of the degree of stratification of society, as it is the process, in many cases, of the cause of the phenomenon of terrorism. Terror intensifies stratification process, which, in turn, forms the basis of the socio-psychological phenomenon of terrorism. The notion of terrorizing is used enhance the stratification of society.

Despite the large number of scientific publications on the study of the phenomenon of "terrorism", there are very few researches on the relationship between this phenomenon and the process of social stratification.

II. THE AIM OF THE WORK

To disclosure stratified nature of the phenomenon of "terrorism".

III. THE METHOD OF SOLUTION

The analysis of current literature and practical experience shows that the generation of terrorism is closely linked to the bundle of socio-economic and political system of the society [12]. But it is necessary to find out the cause of the bundle. However, inadmissible one-sided approach to conclusions about its descent or cause of the bundle; it is necessary to emphasize the debatable issues of the time the emergence of the phenomenon of "terrorism", its manifestations throughout history, which indirectly suggests that historians who study terrorism do not have a common view of this phenomenon [13].

However, the story of the origin of mass terrorism is associated generally with the Great French Revolution (1789-1795), which was accompanied by marching to the massacre of the bourgeoisie with their opponents, and then fratricidal terror against its leaders, including Robespierre [14]. Followed on the revolutionary events of XIX - early XX centuries,

researchers respective to terrorism and terror, have deep roots, and the correlation associated with the process of stratification of society by the transition from one form to another.

Due to the fact that after the Second World War, the phenomenon of "terrorism" becomes the rapid development that has been associated with redistribution of spheres of influence, i.e. establishment of a new stratification of world society. All this was seen by researchers in the second half of XX century as a typical manifestation of terrorism in the examples of Germany, Spain, Italy and Greece. During this period, it may be noted a lot of evidence to support terrorist boom. According to the authors, this period is the era of the generation of the phenomenon of "terrorism" and turning it into a stratum of society. The phenomenon becomes the main features of modern terrorism and enables them to present historical period called the "Age of Terror" [15]. In this case, according to the authors, this period is the era of the generation of the phenomenon of "terrorism." Such features are the unprecedented scale of the shares, the loss of terrorist risk punishment, bigotry, internationalization, that is, the global nature of international terrorism. Here it would be pertinent to note that during the XX century in the social and political sciences, the idea prevailed weakening the role of religion in society. The basic version of this idea is the theory of modernization and secularization [16]. They are based on a premise that the era of religious wars was a thing of the past and history, that's why the impact of Islam on the domestic and foreign policies of Muslim countries is falling. So, right before your eyes there is the stratification of relations not only between religions, but also within one religion, which is reflected in the mechanism of generation of terrorizing.

A striking example is - the theory of clash of civilizations of S. Huntington [17]. Stratification of the socio-economic system of the society in the second half of the XX century provided terrorism with a stable background in the history of the world, changing from episodic events in a permanent risk factor in almost all regions of the world. Under the influence of events September 11, 2001, the issue of Islamism and terrorism filled media and acquired the status of intellectual-political fashion. In this situation even more acute questions are evoked. Today, for many researchers it is obvious that the theoretical solution to the problem of Islamism and terrorism is difficult. Socio-political contexts prevail the analytical principles, but solutions are usually limited to specific aspects of the problem [18].

The complexity of the data analysis and trying to make out conclusions from this situation, in our view, suggests the need for the information model of the phenomenon of "terrorism". On the basis of this model, fundamental analysis of the dialectical nature of the phenomenon of generation of terrorism could be implemented, in order to be able to predict in advance the emergence of this phenomenon. On the other hand, such a model by its nature has to be linked to the process of social stratification. For example, history has shown that during the transitional period, the level of social stratification is increasing dramatically, that is the gap between the layers of population is constantly growing. This

can be explained by poverty, the severe economic crisis, high unemployment, extreme differentiation of population by income, weak government and its failure to ensure the safety of individuals and their property. This creates conditions for social conflict (this is the beginning of stratification), creates a special relationship between different social strata of society, some of which are characterized by inadequate assessment of reality, the mood of uncertainty that has not met expectations, fear, anger, and aggression. In such circumstances, a part of society, not fully exposed to an adequate response, favorably received extremist calls for protests, extremism and cruelty are becoming an integral part of the mentality of society [19]. Such conditions can be a fertile ground for the establishment of a new stratification. All of the above gives us the confidence to create a mathematical model of the phenomenon of terrorism on the basis of socio-psychological analysis of stratification as a specific socio-psychological phenomenon [20]. Such a statement has the objective conditions providing correlation with generation of stratification with phenomenon of terrorism. We give a definition for the term of "stratification" to discover the essence of the concept.

Stratification is well-established, hierarchically organized structure of social inequality that exists in a particular society at a particular point in history. Moreover social inequality is reproduced in stable forms as a reflection of the political, economic and social structure. The existence of social differentiation can be taken for axiom, but an explanation of its nature, the foundations of the historical evolution and the relationship of specific forms remains as one of the key problems of sociology. And in order to understand this, you must understand some of the concepts that form the essence of the problem.

Social stratification is a description of social inequalities in society, its division into social classes by income, presence or absence of privilege, lifestyle and etc.

In the period of primitive society, inequality was not so significant, and because of this phenomenon of stratification was almost absent. As the society is developing, inequality is also rising. In complex societies, inequality divided the people, not only on income but also on the level of education, proximity to power. There were castes, then groups, and then classes arose. In some societies, it is prohibited to pass from one class to another, in some it is limited, and there are others where it is fully allowed. The freedom of social movements helps to identify the way in which a society is open or closed.

Stratification of society is using several factors: income, wealth, power and prestige. Income can be defined as the amount of money that family gained or a single individual or within a certain period of time [21].

Stratification is a process characterized by stratification of society. Management of this process is carried out with the help of the new laws in society. But it should be noted that the flow of this process depend not yet inscribed on the rules of relations between the strata of society.

The following is an example let us consider the effect of stratification on the phenomenon of "terrorism".

So, one of the most notable political and topical forms of social segmentation is ethnic and religious stratification. Stratification is the uneven distribution of ethnic groups interacting in various spheres of life: economic, political, religious. Ethnic and religious inequality in some form is inherent in any society. At each stage of historical development, ethnic and religious stratification had its own characteristics and expressed the interests of various social classes and strata. For example, Nigeria - a country of ethnic pluralism in its territory, home to more than 200 nations with differing levels and features of the socio-economic and cultural development, to religious affiliation, according to the traditions and customs related to the different historical and cultural areas [22]. The region's ethno regional (or ethno) movement was aimed, ultimately, to improve the status of religion in the framework of the existing religious stratification.

The growth of the religious factor in Nigeria, its politicization largely contributed to the failure to resolve the national question of religious, interfaith relations and tensions led solution to their relationship attacks [23].

Another important direction to measure social stratification, as we know, is income and power [24]. The confirmation of this trend of stratification can use the example of Belarus, where there is a cumulative effect of political and economic stratification in the offspring of the phenomenon of "terrorism."

All the current political, economic and socio-negative conflicts have a significant impact on the overall psychology of society, leading to a heightened sense of social instability, insecurity for a significant part of the citizens, despair, radicalization and the growth of social aggression, social frustration, fall of authority of the government and laws, faith in themselves and possibility of positive change.

A third example is Mexico, where the struggle for prestige, income and territory, that is, for the top places in the stratification pyramid between large criminal organizations has meant that there were a number of terrorist acts aimed at the destruction and intimidation of opponents of the authorities and the population [25].

Finally, the story of the end of XX century, showed that during 1991-2000 the country's post-Soviet space in transition and the situation was very unstable politically, economically and socially, and in terms of security of countries and their populations, as in this period in many regions have been committed numerous acts [26] of terrorism to establish new relationships between the stratified strata.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The effects of political and economic stratification of society by causing the phenomenon of "terrorism" are obvious. If you do not manage this process, it is very difficult to predict the product of the phenomenon of "terrorism". Analysis of the dialectical framework for the process of stratification shows the possibility of creating a logical model of information-generation phenomenon "terrorism".

REFERENCES

- [1] E.B.Petrishe, Notes on terrorism, Moscow, Editorial URSS, 2011, p. 9
- [2] Yu. Roostamov, "Terrorism: Concepts, types and distinctive features", Bulletin of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2010, № 1, pp. 44-46
- [3] Tendency of evaluation of terrorism 2012, from <http://privacyandterrorism.org/tendence.php>
- [4] Yu.Roostamov, "Information-psychological aspects of terrorism", 1 Material international scientific-practical conference "Politics and Law in the socio-economic system of society", Moscow, 2011 pp. 281-291.
- [5] Yu.Roostamov, "Socio-psychological and criminal analysis of contemporary terrorism and extremism" Lawyer, 2010, № 3-4, pp. 52-53.
- [6] I.S.Palitay, "Features of the modeling method in the sociological study of terrorism", author's abstract, Moscow, 2009, p. 22.
- [7] See above 2.
- [8] A.H.Imamov, "Terrorism - a form of organized crime", Abstract of doctoral dissertation, Dushanbe, 2003, p. 15
- [9] V.P.Emelyanov, "Terror and terrorism: questions of limits" Law and Policy, 2004, № 4, pp.76-77.
- [10] B.S.Komissarov, B.P.Emelyanov, "Terror, terrorism, "state terrorism" and the concept of the ratio" Bulletin of Moscow University, Series 11, 1999, № 5, pp. 34-35.
- [11] Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On combating terrorism" from 15.12.2000, № 167 – II, Bulletin of OliyMajlis of Uzbekistan, Tashkent - 2001, № 1-2, p. 363.
- [12] I.A.Kirillov, "The Problem of the causes of terrorism", Siberian Law Journal, 2002, № 2.
- [13] T.S.Kozodoy, "The problem of studying the concept of terrorism" Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Natural Sciences, 2006, pp. 87-89.
- [14] G. Chaliand, A. Blin. The history of terrorism: from antiquity to al Qaeda, Univ. of California Press, California - 2007. - VIII, 474 p.
- [15] O.Ryazanov "The era of terror: a war against all" (February 2004) from http://www.bratishka.ru/archiv/2004/2/2004_2_8.php
- [16] L.P. Voronkova, Criticism of theological conceptions of secularism, Moscow: Knowledge – 1987, p. 64.
- [17] Samuel P. Huntington "The Clash of Civilization", Foreign Affairs, 1993, p. 22
- [18] See above 4
- [19] L.Belyaeva, General direction of stratification in transitional period, General trends of stratification in transition, social stratification of Russian society, 1995, p.96
- [20] N.T.Rustamov, B.B.Ibragimov, K.E.Batyrhanov, Modeling of socio-economic stratification systems, Herald ICGS and A. Yasawi, 2012, № 2, p. 58-63.
- [21] K.Davis, The conceptual analysis of stratification, Social Stratification, Ed. Belanovsky S. 1992, № 1, pp. 139-159.
- [22] R.N.Ismagilova, A.Hrushevsky, (1988) The ethnic factor in the political life of Nigeria, Nigeria: Power and Policy, 1988, p. 20.
- [23] N.D.Kosuhin (2006), Africa: the politicization of ethnicity, Bulletin of the Russian University of Peoples' Friendship, Series: Political science. 2006, № 1, pp. 100-108.
- [24] Y.E. Volkov, Sociology of Work, New York, ATISO, 2009, p. 536.
- [25] Dozens killed in Mexico casino attack (August 2011) from <http://euronews.com/2011/08/26/dozens-killed-in-mexico-casino-attack/>
- [26] B.A.Mikhailov, Social structure, social institutions and processes in the region, Tver, 2012, p.69-82. http://edc.tversu.ru/f/uf/040100_68/040100_68_01/m2dv11.pdf